

Medical approach to post-COVID-19 high-grade ventricular arrhythmias: a case report

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Abstract

COVID-19 is a significant risk factor for cardiovascular complications, including arrhythmias, especially in patients with underlying cardiac disease. These risks are particularly pronounced in individuals with pre-existing structural heart abnormalities such as hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM). We present the case of a 50-year-old man with a history of obstructive HCM treated with myectomy and mitral valve replacement, who developed frequent palpitations following a COVID-19 infection. The patient was on bisoprolol and acenocoumarol for blood pressure control and anticoagulation. Physical examination was unremarkable except for a metallic mitral valve tone. ECG showed sinus rhythm with one ventricular extrasystole; echocardiography revealed no new abnormalities. Holter monitoring documented a 10.48% burden of monomorphic ventricular extrasystoles and a non-sustained monomorphic ventricular tachycardia with a warm-up/cool-down phenomenon. Increasing bisoprolol, adding mexiletine, and later combining bisoprolol with amiodarone failed to resolve symptoms. Cardiac MRI showed subepicardial myocardial scarring, suggesting prior myocarditis, but no active inflammation. Ultimately, switching to propranolol 40 mg t.i.d. led to symptom resolution, with no arrhythmias on follow-up. The patient remained stable on propranolol for six months before returning to bisoprolol. This case highlights the potential for COVID-19 to exacerbate arrhythmic complications in HCM and demonstrates the effectiveness of non-selective beta-blockers in resistant arrhythmias.

Keywords

hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, SARS-CoV-2, ventricular tachycardia, beta-blocker, propranolol

Introduction

COVID-19, caused by SARS-CoV-2, has had a significant global impact not only as a respiratory illness but also as a risk factor for cardiovascular diseases (CVD). Recent data show that COVID-19 infection can increase

the risk of a wide range of cardiovascular complications, including myocardial injury, arrhythmias, heart failure, thromboembolic events, and acute coronary syndromes, both during the acute phase and months after infection (Pepera et al. 2022; Vosko et al. 2023; Krishna et al. 2024). Preexisting CVD has also been shown to

aggravate the clinical course of the infection (Elezkurta et al. 2021).

Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM) is characterized by a genetic mutation that leads to myocardial hypertrophy and an increased risk of developing heart failure and malignant arrhythmias. Patients with HCM who contract COVID-19 experience significantly higher rates of total and heart-failure-specific hospitalization, heart failure-related admissions, non-ST elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI), and mortality compared to HCM patients without COVID-19 infection (10.8 vs. 5 per 100 persons). These patients also demonstrate higher levels of systemic inflammation, as evidenced by elevated C-reactive protein (CRP) levels (Saleh et al. 2024).

A retrospective study found that while many HCM patients with COVID-19 recover without major intervention, a notable subset requires hospitalization, and a small percentage experience severe complications such as pulmonary embolism, atrial fibrillation requiring cardioversion, acute decompensated heart failure, mechanical ventilation, or death. Established risk factors for severe COVID-19, such as obesity, appear to be significant drivers of morbidity and mortality in this population (Arabadjian et al. 2021).

COVID-19 infection is associated with a range of cardiac rhythm disturbances, including both bradyarrhythmias and tachyarrhythmias. Proposed mechanisms include direct myocardial injury, cytokine storm, increased sympathetic tone, hypoxia, and drug-induced QT prolongation (Hu et al. 2020; Fagundes et al. 2021).

Atrial fibrillation is the most common tachyarrhythmia in hospitalized COVID-19 patients, reported in 21% of cases (Bhattacharya et al. 2024). Case reports and small series specifically highlight an increased incidence of arrhythmias, most notably atrial fibrillation, in HCM patients following COVID-19 infection. The upregulation of ACE2 receptors (the entry point for SARS-CoV-2) in cardiac tissue may contribute to this susceptibility (Afriz Pasha et al. 2021).

In the general population, arrhythmias have been reported in up to 16% of hospitalized COVID-19 patients, with malignant ventricular arrhythmias and conduction abnormalities being documented. These risks are further increased by the intense inflammatory response and metabolic stress caused by COVID-19, especially in patients with pre-existing cardiac conditions such as HCM (Hu et al. 2020; Fagundes et al. 2021).

COVID-19-related myocarditis is a recognized complication, with symptoms including tachycardia, ST-segment alterations, T wave inversion, and left ventricular hypertrophy (Demmer et al. 2022). Among cardiomyopathies observed in COVID-19 patients, various types—including stress-induced and dilated cardiomyopathy—have been reported (Omidi et al. 2021). Arrhythmias in COVID-19 can range from benign premature beats to life-threatening ventricular tachycardia/fibrillation and conduction disorders (Fagundes et al. 2021; Omidi et al. 2021).

Acknowledging the established link between COVID-19 and adverse cardiovascular outcomes, we present a case

of a medical approach to the treatment of a 50-year-old patient with previously diagnosed HCM who developed new-onset palpitations following COVID-19 infection. This case highlights the potential for SARS-CoV-2 to worsen arrhythmic complications in this vulnerable population, as well as demonstrating the effectiveness of non-selective beta-blockers in managing resistant arrhythmias.

Case presentation

We present a case of a 50-year-old patient who sought ambulatory medical care for frequent palpitations, which occurred following a COVID-19 infection. Five years prior, the patient underwent surgical treatment for obstructive hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, which included a surgical myectomy and mitral valve replacement. The patient was taking bisoprolol for ambulatory blood pressure control and acenocoumarol for his mechanical valve.

On physical examination, no abnormalities were detected. A loud metallic tone from the mechanical mitral valve was audible, with no additional murmurs. A standard 12-lead ECG was performed and showed sinus rhythm with one ventricular extrasystole (VES) recorded (Fig. 1).

Echocardiography revealed no newly developed structural or functional abnormalities. The patient underwent 24-hour Holter ECG monitoring, which showed a VES burden of 10.48% with monomorphic VES and an episode of non-sustained monomorphic ventricular tachycardia (VT) with a warm-up/cool-down phenomenon. These findings necessitated a change in the patient's antiarrhythmic regimen, beginning with an increased dose of bisoprolol to the maximum tolerated level. Cardiac magnetic resonance imaging was scheduled and revealed myocardial scarring, particularly in the subepicardial region around the lateral wall of the left ventricle—findings consistent with previous myocarditis. The absence of myocardial edema and lack of increased contrast uptake were interpreted as signs of no active inflammatory process; therefore, no anti-inflammatory treatment was initiated.

The patient was followed up and continued to report persistent palpitations, unaffected by bisoprolol therapy. This prompted the addition of mexiletine at standard dosage, which also failed to relieve symptoms. Due to continued complaints, a different strategy was adopted: combination therapy with bisoprolol and amiodarone. Amiodarone was administered as a loading dose for several weeks, followed by a maintenance dose.

On subsequent follow-up, the patient reported no improvement in symptoms, and VES remained detectable on ECG. As a final noninvasive pharmacological approach, monotherapy with propranolol 40 mg t.i.d. was initiated. This change to a non-selective beta-blocker resulted in symptom resolution. During regular follow-up visits, the patient reported no complaints and showed no signs of arrhythmia recurrence. He remained on propranolol therapy for six months, after which he was transitioned back to bisoprolol.

Figure 1. 12-lead ECG.

Discussion

Cardiac complications in patients who have been infected with COVID-19 are relatively common (Vosko et al. 2023). These can manifest as rhythm and conduction disturbances or acute or chronic heart failure due to myocardial damage and pericardial inflammation. The exact mechanism by which the viral infection leads to cardiac involvement is still not completely clear. Direct cardiac involvement has been the primary speculated mechanism, with viral cell entry through the ACE2 receptor (Bielecka-Dabrowa et al. 2021). However, new data have emerged suggesting a potential role for virus-triggered myocardial damage. Two potential mechanisms have been proposed. One is antigen mimicry from the spike protein that induces a cross-reactive immune response against the host's cardiomyocytes (Arévalo-Cortés et al. 2024). Another recently proposed mechanism involves adipocytes. A high viral load has been isolated from human adipocytes in patients infected with COVID-19. Infected adipocytes have been shown to shift their cytokine secretion to a proinflammatory phenotype. Elevated levels of IP-10, PDGF-AA, PDGF-AB/BB, IL-4, macrophage migration inhibitory factor (MIF), vascular endothelial growth factor A (VEGF), and macrophage colony-stimulating factor 1 (M-CSF) have been reported, which could increase the systemic severity of the infection (Martínez-Colón et al. 2022).

Arrhythmias are among the more frequent cardiac complications observed in patients with COVID-19, regardless of pre-existing heart disease. The most common type of arrhythmia is atrial fibrillation (AF) (Duckheim and Schreieck 2021). Patients with concomitant heart disease, such as hypertrophic cardiomyopathy—which is itself proarrhythmogenic—have an even higher risk of developing life-threatening arrhythmias. Arrhythmias can develop

through any of three main mechanisms: reentry, triggered activity, or automaticity. The presence of a warm-up/cool-down phenomenon in our patient suggests that automaticity may be the primary mechanism at play. Abnormal automaticity is observed in conditions where the resting diastolic membrane potential is driven toward the threshold potential, leading to membrane depolarization and impulse generation. Such conditions include hyperkalemia, intracellular acidosis, or catecholamine excess (Gaztañaga et al. 2012). Other viral infections have been reported to cause automaticity-induced VT (Tai et al. 1992), but no cases related to COVID-19 have been described so far. In vitro studies have reported post-COVID-19 impairment in calcium handling in cardiomyocytes, with increased calcium leakage and elevated intracellular calcium levels, which could serve as a substrate for arrhythmias (Dimai et al. 2021).

Propranolol, a pharmaceutical compound classified as a β -adrenergic receptor antagonist, was initially developed for the treatment of arrhythmias (Abdullah and Al-Kinani 2024). Its effectiveness in treating our patient's arrhythmias is likely due to its non-selective beta receptor inhibition. During electrophysiological studies, arrhythmias based on abnormal automaticity are typically induced by infusion of non-selective beta agonists, which explains the success of propranolol in this case. None of the other medications used in the early phase of the patient's treatment had any inhibitory effect on β_2 receptors.

Cardiac arrhythmias are inherently complex due to the diversity of underlying mechanisms. There are few non-invasive indicators that can help determine the primary mechanism responsible for an arrhythmia. Arrhythmias that are not affected by changes in heart rate and are unresponsive to potent antiarrhythmic drugs may be suspected to arise from abnormal automaticity. The use

of propranolol in contemporary medical practice is rare. The availability of alternative medications with fewer side effects and simpler dosing regimens makes propranolol a less favorable option. Nonetheless, its classical non-selective beta-blocking properties make it a unique and potent antiarrhythmic choice in difficult-to-control cases.

Conclusion

This case highlights the increased risk of arrhythmic complications in patients with hypertrophic cardiomyopathy following COVID-19 infection and also demonstrates the potential effectiveness of non-selective beta-blockers such as propranolol in managing refractory ventricular arrhythmias in this population.

Careful monitoring and individualized treatment are crucial to improving patient outcomes in such complex cases.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Clinic of Cardiology, St. George University Hospital, Plovdiv, Bulgaria. Patient anonymity has been preserved throughout.

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Use of AI

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Author contributions

S.K.: conceptualization of the study, patient management, manuscript drafting, and critical revisions; M.H.: literature review, data collection, and interpretation of clinical findings; M.F.K.: preparation of figures and discussion section; V.A.: diagnostic data analysis, cardiological evaluation, and clinical correlation; A.M.: pharmacological review and contribution to manuscript editing; L.K.: supervision, final approval of the manuscript, and overall coordination of the study. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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